

Methodology for Designing Stable Forced-Ranking Questionnaires

Based on Text Embeddings

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Abstract

This paper presents an engineering methodology for designing forced-ranking survey questions (five-item rankings) interpreted using text embeddings and cosine similarity to semantic axes. Unlike classical score-based scales, the embedding-based approach allows the same response to be interpreted relative to multiple axes without increasing questionnaire length.

A key practical issue of embedding-based questionnaires is interpretation instability: semantically close answer formulations tend to collapse in vector space, leading to differences in ranking across language models and even across independent sessions of the same model.

This version of the preprint proposes a reproducible protocol for designing formulations, based on the use of LLMs as a diagnostic tool. Three empirical cases using real formulations are presented: an unstable ranking, a stabilized ranking after minimal linguistic revisions, and a ranking exhibiting intra-model instability. It is shown that the stability of embedding-based interpretation is a property of linguistic design of items and axes, rather than of the scoring formula.

1. Introduction

The use of text embeddings opens the possibility of an alternative interpretation of responses in questionnaires and assessment systems. Unlike classical psychometric methods, where each question is rigidly tied to a single scale, embedding-based interpretation allows the same response to be mapped to multiple semantic axes. This approach can potentially reduce questionnaire length and increase the expressiveness of respondent profiles, but it requires careful linguistic design of formulations.

In the first version of this work, a general approach to interpreting ranked responses using text embeddings was proposed. The present version develops this approach by focusing on engineering aspects of formulation design and on demonstrating the behavior of embedding-based interpretation through concrete, reproducible examples. In particular, the second version examines cases of both stable and unstable ranking in detail, making it possible to move from a conceptual description of the method to a practical protocol for its application.

In contrast to psychometric research, the focus here is not on construct validity, but on the reproducibility of interpretation in embedding space.

2. Data Format and Interpretation Method

A **forced-ranking** format is used: respondents are asked to order five answer options.

Each option is encoded as an embedding of the string:

```
"<question text> <answer option>"
```

(embedding model: `embedding-3-small`).

Based on the ranking, a weighted average embedding of the respondent's answer, denoted as v , is constructed, where higher-ranked options receive greater weight.

Interpretation is performed relative to an axis defined by two texts—a positive (pos) and a negative (neg) pole—both of which are also encoded as embeddings. The final score is computed as:

```
score = cos(v, pos) - cos(v, neg)
```

3. Design Methodology

The methodology for designing stable forced-ranking items is based on iterative alignment of interpretations across language models, where an LLM acts both as an interpreter and as a generator of wording revisions.

The process includes the following steps:

1. **Testing across multiple models.**

The same testing prompt (Appendix B) is used in two different language models. Each model ranks the items relative to the axis and provides an explanation of its ranking.

2. **Capturing disagreement and forming the revision context.**

If the orderings differ, the ranking and explanation from Model B are appended under the result from Model A. It is then stated explicitly that the models produced different orders and that the items must be revised.

3. **LLM-generated item revisions for alignment.**

The LLM is asked to revise the item wordings so that:

- items remain short;
- axis texts are not changed;
- the question is not changed whenever possible;
- both models converge to the same ordering relative to the axis.

In some iterations, additional guidance is provided:

- highlighting specific items that appear ambiguous;
- requesting a structural change, such as adding a new “top” or “bottom” item if a disputed item keeps getting “stuck” in the middle and cannot be stabilized.

4. **Re-testing and repeating until stability.**

The revised items are re-tested using the same prompt (Appendix B) in both models. The cycle is repeated until inter-model stability (C2) is achieved and, when needed, intra-model stability (C1).

Thus, stability is achieved through linguistic design of items rather than through changing the scoring formula, using LLMs as tools for generating and validating revisions.

4. Stability Criteria

Two criteria are used:

C1. Intra-model stability — the same model returns the same ordering of options across multiple independent sessions.

C2. Inter-model stability — different models return the same ordering of options relative to the axis.

5. Empirical Cases

Axis

Psychological Safety (positive pole)

I create an environment where people are not afraid to make mistakes, speak freely, receive support and respect. I listen, clarify, strengthen ideas, seek to understand others’ motives, and do not judge harshly.

Psychological Safety (negative pole)

I often judge ideas harshly, quickly point out mistakes, demand precision and discipline, and may exert pressure. People around me tend to avoid showing weakness and behave formally.

5.1 Case 1 — Inter-model Instability

Ranking

When people make mistakes, I

- move on without discussion
- analyze the cause of the mistake
- support a new attempt
- look for solution options
- take part of the responsibility

If an idea is controversial, I

- stay on the sidelines
- criticize the logic
- propose an alternative option
- develop strong points
- seek points of agreement

During discussion, it is easier for me to

- dominate the discussion
- identify the core and next steps
- bring positions to a decision
- let everyone speak
- create a comfortable atmosphere

If I disagree, I

- point out mistakes
- withdraw from the discussion
- explain my position
- ask clarifying questions
- seek common ground and shared goals

When someone is confused, I

- ask them to be clearer
- guide them through structure and pace
- ask questions to help
- help formulate the thought
- reduce stress and provide support

Observation:

Across models, the ordering of items diverges, primarily within the group of “positive” reactions (support, analysis, responsibility, solution-seeking).

5.2 Case 2 — Inter-model Stability

Ranking

When people make mistakes, I

- move on without discussion
- discuss what can be improved
- help continue the work
- support a new attempt
- say that it is normal

If an idea is controversial, I

- stay on the sidelines
- criticize the logic
- propose an alternative option
- develop strong points
- seek points of agreement

During discussion, it is easier for me to

- dominate the discussion
- identify the core and next steps
- bring positions to a decision
- let everyone speak
- create a comfortable atmosphere

If I disagree, I

- point out mistakes
- tactfully end the conversation
- calmly explain my position
- ask questions to understand
- seek common ground and shared goals

When someone is confused, I

- make a remark about clarity
- guide through structure and pace
- ask questions to help
- help formulate the thought
- support and reduce stress

Observation:

Different models converge on the same ordering of items relative to the psychological safety axis.

5.3 Case 3 — Intra-model Instability

Ranking

When people make mistakes, I

- discuss alternatives
- help understand the mistake
- suggest trying again
- share responsibility
- move on to the next step

If an idea is controversial, I

- look for what can be strengthened
- bring positions together
- clarify the logic
- propose alternatives
- remain neutral

If I disagree, I

- ask questions
- look for points of overlap
- offer gentle criticism
- explain my perspective
- postpone the discussion

During discussion, it is easier for me to

- create a comfortable atmosphere
- find what suits everyone
- notice what others missed
- guide the conversation
- focus on the core of the task

When someone is confused, I

- ask clarifying questions
- help formulate the thought
- give the person time to collect themselves
- support the idea if I agree
- propose a discussion structure

When I am criticized, I

- look for value in the feedback
- analyze what I can improve
- ask for examples and specifics
- clarify details
- remain calm

In a team conflict, I

- reduce emotions through conversation
- clarify misunderstandings
- seek compromise
- suggest a pause
- bring everyone back to the facts

Observation:

Across repeated runs of the same model, the ordering of items changes; intra-model stability is not achieved.

6. Discussion

All three cases demonstrate that instability in embedding-based interpretation arises from semantic “collapse” of items, even when formulations are logically correct and positive. Stability is achieved through linguistic differentiation of action types, levels of agency, and modes of response.

The methodology makes it possible to systematically identify and eliminate instability without complicating the scoring formula or increasing questionnaire length.

7. Limitations

The methodology is optimized for a specific embedding model and text encoding scheme. Changing the model requires re-testing. The work does not claim psychometric validity and is not intended for clinical use.

8. Ethical Considerations

The methodology is not intended for medical or clinical diagnostics. Its use assumes voluntary participation, minimization of collected data, and transparent description of response interpretation procedures.

Appendix A. Design Prompt

Context: I am designing a system of forced-ranking questions (five-item rankings) evaluated using embedding-3-small. Each ranking item is encoded as a text embedding: "<short question text> <answer option>". A weighted average embedding of the respondent's answer is then constructed and compared to one or more axes using cosine similarity (pos / neg).

Task: Help design questions, answer options, and axis texts such that embedding-3-small can **reliably and stably** distinguish and rank the options.

Constraints and requirements (mandatory):

1. **!** Do not use abstract values without action (e.g., "responsibility," "results," "development").
Each option must include:
 - o an action,
 - o an agent (who acts),
 - o if necessary, a context or level (strategy / process / people).
2. **!** Avoid semantic collapse of options.
If two options can be substituted without loss of meaning, the embedding will merge them. Such options must be lexically separated.
3. **!** One question = one managerial or behavioral scenario.
Do not mix different decision levels within one question (e.g., strategy + operations + values).
4. **!** Axis texts (pos / neg) must be:
 - o logically consistent,
 - o single-competency,
 - o mirror images of each other,
 - o free of a generic "good person" portrait.
5. **!** If a question contains two clearly "bad" patterns, it is acceptable that embeddings cannot stably order them. In this case:
 - o either treat them as equivalent "bottom,"
 - o or refine the negative axis rather than the options.
6. **!** Minimal edits have priority.
If a problem can be solved by adding 1-2 words, do not rewrite everything.
7. **!** The question must be under 25 characters; each option under 30 characters.

Process:

- First propose the question formulation.
- Then provide five answer options (short, semantically distinct).
- Then provide texts for the pos and neg axes.
- Then specify the expected stable ordering of options relative to the pos axis.
- If there are potential edge cases, indicate them immediately.

Important:

Work not as a psychologist or theorist, but as an engineer who anticipates where embedding-3-small may become confused and prevents this at the language level.

Appendix B. Testing Prompt

There is a ranking in which a person must order five options.

Each ranking option is an embedding produced by the embedding-3-small model from the text consisting of the ranking title followed by the option text.

After the person orders the options, the system constructs a weighted average embedding of the response, where higher-ranked options receive greater weight. The response embedding is then compared to the axis embedding, also produced by embedding-3-small, using cosine similarity. If two axis embeddings are given, one representing the positive pole and the other the negative pole, the score is computed as:

$$\text{score} = \cos(\text{item}, \text{pos}) - \cos(\text{item}, \text{neg})$$

Task:

Rank the options by proximity to the axis.

Inputs:

ranking title:

options:

text for axis embedding (pos):

text for axis embedding (neg):

Appendix C. Item Alignment Prompt

Another LLM model ranks these items differently, even though it received the same task and the same axes.

Revise the items so that they remain short,
but are ranked identically and as stably as possible by both models.

Leave unchanged those pairs of adjacent items whose ranking order совпадает in both cases.

If necessary:

- you may modify individual items;
- you may add a new item at the top or bottom instead of a disputed one, if the disputed item gets stuck in the middle and cannot be stabilized.

*The ranking produced by the second model,
together with its explanation of each item's position,
is then appended to the context.*